

RAPPORT

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Analyse bibliométrique de la recherche sur la santé mentale en milieu de travail au Canada, 1991-2002

Éric Archambault*, Grégoire Côté*,
et Yves Gingras ‡

Traduit de l'anglais par André LeBlanc

* Science-Metrix et ‡ CIRST-OST

Préparé pour
l'Institut des neurosciences, de la santé mentale et des toxicomanies
et l'Institut de la santé publique et des populations
Les Instituts de recherche en santé du Canada

Adresse : Centre interuniversitaire de recherche sur la science et la technologie
Observatoire des sciences et des technologies
Université du Québec à Montréal
Pavillon Thérèse-Casgrain, 3^e étage
455, boul. René-Lévesque Est, Bureau W-3040
Montréal (Québec)
Canada H2L 4Y2

Téléphone : (514) 987-4018

Télécopieur : (514) 987-7726

Courriel : cirst@uqam.ca

Internet : www.cirst.uqam.ca – www.ost.uqam.ca

Science-Metrix

Adresse : Science-Metrix
4572, avenue de Lorimier
Montréal (Québec)
Canada H2H 2B5

Téléphone : (514) 495-6505

Télécopieur : (514) 495-6523

Courriel : info@science-metrix.com

Internet : www.science-metrix.com

Points saillants de l'étude

- Cette étude utilise Medline, une banque de données de publications dans le domaine des sciences biomédicales, pour mesurer la production scientifique sur la santé mentale en milieu de travail (SMMT) au cours de la période 1991-2002 aux plans mondial, canadien, provincial, urbain et institutionnel.
- Bien que les maladies mentales en milieu de travail soient très coûteuses au plan économique, la recherche dans ce champ demeure négligeable aux échelles mondiales et canadiennes – seulement 0,2 % des publications biomédicales se penchent sur la question.
- Malgré ce faible niveau de production, le nombre de publications a doublé et triplé pendant les douze dernières années aux échelles mondiales et canadiennes respectivement.
- Sur le plan provincial, l'Ontario, le Québec, la Colombie-Britannique et l'Alberta mènent en nombre absolu de publications. L'Ontario est de loin le premier, autant par l'ampleur de sa production absolue que par celle de son rendement par personne. Il est également spécialisé dans ce champ de recherche.
- Bien qu'ils ne se démarquent pas en termes absolus, la Nouvelle-Écosse et le Manitoba jouent des rôles importants étant donné leur taille.
- Toronto et Montréal sont les plus importants producteurs de publications sur la SMMT à l'échelle urbaine.
- Les institutions les plus importantes quant au nombre de publications sur la SMMT sont McMaster University, Université de Montréal, University of Toronto, University of British Columbia et University of Western Ontario.
- McMaster University, Université Laval et York University sont les universités ayant le plus grand nombre de chercheurs actifs en SMMT.

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Méthodes

En collaboration avec des experts nommés par l'Institut des neurosciences, de la santé mentale et des toxicomanies (INSMT) et l'Institut de la santé publique et des populations (ISPP) et les Instituts de recherche en santé du Canada (IRSC), l'équipe OST/Science-Metrix a établi un vocabulaire contrôlé qui définit précisément le champ de la recherche sur la santé mentale en milieu de travail. Ce vocabulaire a été validé en notant le pourcentage de publications provenant de revues spécialisées que ces mots clés ont réussi à sélectionner. En se servant de ces mots clés, l'équipe OST/Science-Metrix a produit les statistiques de cette étude à partir de la banque de données Medline, elle-même construite par le US National Library of Medicine.

Cette base de données a été reconstituée par Science-Metrix en vue de produire des statistiques sur les publications scientifiques dans le secteur de la biomédecine et de la médecine clinique. La construction des données pour cette analyse scientométrique a été basée essentiellement sur les termes vedettes-matières en médecine (MeSH). Ces termes constituent un vocabulaire contrôlé pour répertorier les articles dans Medline. Cette étude se sert de la conjugaison des termes MeSH qui relèvent du champ de la santé mentale (ex. “ Stress, Psychological ”) avec ceux qui relèvent du milieu de travail (ex. “ Occupational Diseases ”) pour identifier les articles ayant un canadien comme premier auteur.

Il convient d'émettre une mise en garde concernant l'usage de cette banque de données : seule l'adresse du premier auteur est répertoriée. Cela veut dire que le nombre de publications canadiennes obtenu ici représente le minimum puisqu'il ne prend pas en compte l'existence de publications à multiples auteurs. Aussi, puisque Medline couvre principalement les champs de la biomédecine et de la médecine clinique, il peut manquer certaines publications des sciences humaines et sociales. En général, cependant, les statistiques comparatives et relatives ne devraient pas être affectées. Et puisque le but de cette étude est de cartographier la distribution de l'expertise canadienne plutôt que d'identifier chacun des chercheurs séparément, cette limitation n'est pas un handicap.

Les données ont été utilisées pour produire des statistiques détaillées selon les indicateurs suivants :

Nombre de publications - Nombre de publications scientifiques écrites par des auteurs à l'intérieur d'une entité géographique, géopolitique ou organisationnelle quelconque (ex. pays, villes ou institutions).

Nombre de publications par personne - Il s'agit d'une mesure relative qui prend en compte la taille des entités géographiques en question.

Indice de spécialisation - Il s'agit d'un indicateur d'intensité de la recherche dans une entité géographique ou organisationnelle donnée par rapport à la production globale pour une unité de référence appropriée. Par exemple, si le pourcentage des publications ontariennes (l'entité géographique) dans le champ de la recherche sur la santé mentale en milieu de travail est plus important que le pourcentage de publications dans ce champ à l'échelle canadienne (la référence), l'Ontario est considéré comme étant spécialisé dans ce champ.

Dans le cadre de ce rapport, les indicateurs pertinents ont été utilisés pour les données agrégées par province, par ville, par institution et par chercheur de premier rang.

1. Introduction

Ce rapport examine la production scientifique des chercheurs canadiens dans le champ de la santé mentale en milieu de travail (SMMT) à l'aide des méthodes scientométriques et de la base de données Medline. La production au cours des douze dernières années (1991-2002) est étudiée dans la section 1 et, dans la section 2, la production canadienne est comparée à celle de l'ensemble du monde. Le rapport montre que le Canada affiche un pourcentage légèrement plus élevé de publications dans le champ de la santé mentale en milieu de travail que la moyenne mondiale.

La section 3 examine la production scientifique des provinces canadiennes. Fait peu étonnant, l'Ontario occupe sans contredit la première place en importance, suivi par le Québec en deuxième place, et par la Colombie-Britannique et l'Alberta. Bien que ces provinces mènent en termes absolus, la Nouvelle-Écosse et le Manitoba se démarquent quant à eux en termes relatifs (publications par personne ; indice de spécialisation). La section 4 considère la recherche sur la santé mentale en milieu de travail aux plans urbain et institutionnel, tandis que la section 5 identifie les chercheurs les plus actifs dans le domaine.

2. La production scientifique au plan mondial

Le graphique 1 montre que le pourcentage de publications sur la SMMT augmente plus rapidement au Canada qu'à l'échelle mondiale. En fait, la proportion des publications sur la SMMT est presque 50 % plus élevée au Canada que dans l'ensemble du monde – plus de 0,3 % au Canada contre plus de 0,2 % dans le monde. Bien que la proportion des publications canadiennes sur la SMMT ait chuté sensiblement en 1995 et 1996, il y a toutefois une tendance dans le secteur biomédical au Canada à écrire de plus en plus de publications en SMMT. En effet, la proportion de publications écrites dans ce champ a augmenté pendant huit des douze années étudiées. Il est à noter que les variations annuelles observées ici ne sont pas exceptionnelles pour un petit champ scientifique et que le champ va sans doute faire preuve de plus de stabilité si la croissance se maintient.

Graphique 1. Part de publications sur la SMMT au Canada et dans le monde par année, 1991-2002

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

Le graphique 2 montre qu'entre 1991 et 2002 les publications sur la SMMT ont augmenté de 75 % en termes absolus à l'échelle mondiale, soit de 535 publications en 1990 à 940 en 2002. Au Canada, la croissance a été encore plus importante : la production a plus que triplé, allant de 14 publications en 1991 à 52 en 2002 et la part des publications sur la SMMT écrites au Canada a plus que doublé, allant de 2,6 % en 1991 à 5,5 % en 2002. En moyenne, le Canada a été responsable de 4,4 % des publications sur la SMMT, et a écrit 3,7 % des publications dans le champ biomédical tel qu'indexé par Medline. Ceci signifie que le Canada se spécialise dans le domaine de la SMMT (indice de spécialisation de 1,2). En comparaison, le Canada produit environ 4 % de la littérature scientifique mondiale en sciences naturelles et en génie.

Bien que la production totale soit petite par rapport aux coûts économiques de la maladie mentale en milieu de travail, il est clair que le champ croît rapidement à l'échelle mondiale et encore plus au Canada.

Graphique 2. Publications sur la SMMT au Canada et dans le monde par année, 1991-2002

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

3. La production scientifique au plan provincial

Au Canada, l'Ontario est clairement en avance par rapport aux autres provinces dans le champ de la SMMT. Sa proportion de la production canadienne correspond à plus du double de celle de son plus proche rival, le Québec (46 % des publications canadiennes sur la SMMT sont écrites en Ontario contre 21 % au Québec). La Colombie-Britannique et l'Alberta sont au même niveau, avec chacun 9 % de la production canadienne. Ensemble, le Manitoba et la Saskatchewan comptent pour 8 % des publications, tandis que les provinces de l'Atlantique en comptent pour 7 %. Cette distribution est semblable à celle de toutes les disciplines scientifiques confondues. Par exemple, l'Ontario a produit 45 % des publications en provenance du Canada dans le Science Citation Index en 2002, le Québec 24 % et la Colombie-Britannique 14 %.

* Prairies : Manitoba, Saskatchewan et Alberta

** Atlantique : Terre-Neuve, Île-du-Prince-Édward, Nouvelle-Écosse et Nouveau-Brunswick

Graphique 3. Part de la production scientifique sur la SMMT des provinces canadiennes, 1991-2002

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

Le tableau 1 montre que la production sur la SMMT augmente continuellement en Ontario et en Colombie-Britannique. Le Québec, l'Alberta et les plus petites provinces ont une production plus irrégulière. Cependant, le nombre de publications est assez petit au niveau des provinces, et l'on doit interpréter ces statistiques avec précaution.

Tableau 1 Nombre de publications en recherche sur la SMMT par province canadienne, 1991-2002

Province	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
Ontario	26	31	55	65	177
Québec	14	13	27	26	80
Colombie-Britannique	4	6	11	15	36
Alberta	9	4	6	15	34
Nouvelle-Écosse	3	3	7	7	20
Manitoba	4	8	4	3	19
Saskatchewan	1	3	2	4	10
Nouveau-Brunswick		1		1	2
Terre-Neuve	1			1	2
Île-du-Prince-Édouard			1		1
Canada TOTAL	62	69	113	137	381

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

Le graphique 4 montre que le Manitoba, qui n'est pourtant pas un gros producteur dans l'ensemble, occupe la première place en matière de publications par personne. Elle confirme aussi la position de premier rang qu'occupe l'Ontario et montre que, étant donné sa grandeur, l'Alberta est elle aussi un important producteur de publications sur la SMMT. En revanche, la Colombie-Britannique est au-dessous de la production moyenne par personne au Canada. La Nouvelle-Écosse, qui apparaît avec les provinces de l'Atlantique, se classe bien en termes de publications par personne.

Graphique 4. Publications par million d'habitants par province, 1991-2002

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

Le graphique 5 montre que, bien que la production globale des provinces de l'Atlantique ne soit pas élevée, elle est toutefois plus importante que celle des sciences biomédicales en général ; en d'autres termes, ces provinces se spécialisent en SMMT. Dans le tableau 1, on voit d'emblée que c'est la Nouvelle-Écosse qui soutient les provinces de l'Atlantique en matière de spécialisation. Le Manitoba se classe en deuxième position après ces provinces, ce qui confirme qu'en termes relatifs, le Manitoba occupe une place de première importance en SMMT au Canada. L'Ontario se spécialise, lui aussi, dans ce champ, confirmant ainsi sa position de premier rang dans la recherche sur la SMMT en termes absolus au Canada. Cette position est également confirmée par deux mesures relatives (soit les publications par personne et l'indice de spécialisation). La Saskatchewan, le Québec, la Colombie-Britannique et l'Alberta ne se spécialisent pas dans ce champ.

Il est important de noter que, puisque la recherche en SMMT semble être au stade de l'émergence au Canada, ces données pourraient changer dans un avenir proche, non seulement en matière de publications par personne mais aussi en matière d'indice de spécialisation.

Graphique 5. Indice de spécialisation des provinces canadiennes, 1991-2002.

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

4. La production scientifique aux plans urbain et institutionnel

Le tableau 2 montre qu'au plan urbain, Toronto occupe clairement la première place en matière de SMMT. On voit aussi que sa production croît de façon régulière. Montréal occupe la deuxième place, et Vancouver la troisième. London et Hamilton viennent compléter ce classement des premières villes canadiennes en SMMT, avec au moins deux publications par année en moyenne. Winnipeg, Edmonton, Québec, Ottawa et Halifax ont tous au moins une publication en SMMT par année en moyenne. Halifax est la seule ville de la région Atlantique qui se classe parmi les villes canadiennes les plus productives en SMMT, ayant produit au moins 6 publications au cours de la période 1991-2002.

Tableau 2 Les villes canadiennes les plus productives en recherche sur la SMMT, 1991-2002*

Ville	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
Toronto	11	16	19	33	79
Montréal	11	8	18	18	55
Vancouver	4	4	10	12	30
London	4	3	11	10	28
Hamilton	3	5	9	9	26
Winnipeg	4	8	4	3	19
Edmonton	7	2	3	7	19
Québec	1	5	7	6	19
Ottawa	3	1	5	7	16
Halifax	3	2	2	6	13
Calgary	1	1	1	7	10
Kingston	2	1	3	3	9
Saskatoon	1	1	2	2	6
Wolfville		1	4	1	6

* Villes qui ont produit un minimum de 6 publications au cours de la période (1991-2002)
Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

Aucune institution ne ressort clairement comme étant une très grande productrice de publications sur la SMMT. En fait, le chef de file, McMaster University, ne dispose, en moyenne, que de deux publications par année dans ce champ. Les autres universités de premier rang, soit l'Université de Montréal, University of Toronto, University of British Columbia et University of Western Ontario, ont toutes en moyenne au moins 1,5 publications par année. Bien que le Manitoba se distingue au niveau provincial quant à son volume de production, University of Manitoba n'a réussi qu'à produire une publication en SMMT par année en moyenne.

Tableau 3 Les institutions canadiennes les plus productives en recherche sur la SMMT, 1991-2002*

Institution	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
McMaster University	2	4	9	9	24
Université de Montréal	2	6	3	10	21
University of Toronto	3	6	2	10	21
University of British Columbia	2	3	7	7	19
University of Western Ontario	4	2	5	7	18
Centre for Addiction and Mental Health	6	2	5	4	17
Université Laval		5	7	4	16
University of Alberta	6	1	3	5	15
York University	2	3	2	7	14
University of Manitoba	2	6	1	3	12
UQÀM	3	1	6	2	12
McGill University	5		2	2	9
Dalhousie University	3	1	1	3	8
Queen's University	1	1	3	3	8
University of Calgary	1	1	1	5	8
Acadia University		1	4	1	6
Institute for Work & Health			1	5	6
University Health Network			3	3	6

* Institutions ayant produit un minimum de 6 publications au cours de la période (1991-2002)

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

5. La production scientifique au plan de la recherche

Le tableau 4 présente les chercheurs qui ont produit au moins trois publications dans le champ de la SMMT. Ces données ont été validées à la main afin de détecter les dénombrements homonymiques erronés¹ et de déterminer les affiliations des auteurs. L'annexe 2 répertorie tous les auteurs qui ont produit au moins une publication sur la SMMT entre 1991 et 2002, et dont la publication indexée dans Medline contient un premier auteur canadien.

McMaster University occupe la première place parmi les centres de recherche sur la SMMT au Canada, car ayant le plus grand nombre de publications par institution, elle a aussi le plus grand nombre d'auteurs sur la liste des chercheurs les plus actifs dans le champ (sept auteurs). Le Centre de toxicomanie et de santé mentale (CTSM) et l'Université Laval, qui se sont classés respectivement sixième et septième en tant qu'institutions les plus actives en SMMT, se sont retrouvés en seconde position en ce qui concerne le nombre de chercheurs les plus actifs (quatre chacun). L'Institut de recherche sur le travail et la santé et l'UQÀM ont chacun trois chercheurs de premier rang, alors qu'Acadia University, Université de Montréal, University of Toronto et York University en ont deux chacune.

Bien que la plupart des chercheurs les plus actifs soient au sein des universités, certains proviennent aussi du CTSM (comme nous l'avons vu ci-dessus), du Centre hospitalier affilié universitaire de Québec (CHA Québec), de l'Hôpital Douglas à Montréal, de Santé Canada et de l'Institut de recherche sur le travail et la santé – ainsi, environ un quart des chercheurs de premier rang travaillent en dehors d'une université (cela ne veut pas dire que ces centres ne soient pas pour autant affiliés à une université).

¹ Par exemple, Tremblay, J. pourrait en fait être deux auteurs, ex. Joséphine Tremblay ou Joseph Tremblay. Ce serait évidemment une erreur d'attribuer 10 publications à un J. Tremblay si Joséphine en avait écrites 6 et Joseph 4. La validation exige que l'on vérifie les publications une à une afin de s'assurer que les décomptes d'un auteur proviennent d'un seul chercheur plutôt que d'homonymes.

Tableau 4 Les chercheurs canadiens les plus productifs en recherche sur la SMMT, 1991-2002*

Nom	Institution	Unité de recherche en santé des populations
Asmundson, Gord	University of Regina	Faculty of Kinesiology and Health Studies
Beiser, Morton	CAMH	Social, Prevention and Health Policy Research Dept.
Berkowitz, Jonathan	University of British Columbia	Department of Family Practice
Bourbonnais, Renée	Université Laval	Département de réadaptation
Boyer, Richard	Université de Montréal	Centre de recherche Fernand-Seguin
Brisson, Chantal	Université Laval	Département de médecine sociale et préventive
Brunet, Alain	Douglas Hospital	Department of Psychiatry
Burke, Ronald J.	York University	Schulich School of Business
Chappell, Neena L.	University of Victoria	Centre on Aging
Cherry, Nicola	University of Alberta	Department of Public Health Sciences
Cole, Donald C.	Institute for Work & Health	
Cunningham, Charles	McMaster University	Dept. of Psychiatry & Behavioural Neurosciences
Dewa, Carolyn	CAMH	Social Prevention and Health Policy Research Dept.
Duquette, André	Université de Montréal	Faculte des sciences infirmieres
Eyles, John	McMaster University	Department of Clinical Epidemiology & Biostatistics
Glancy, Graham D.	McMaster University	Department of Psychiatry
Goering, Paula	CAMH	Social Prevention and Health Policy Research Dept.
Gottlieb, B. H.	University of Guelph	Department of Psychology
Greenglass, Esther	York University	Department of Psychology
Harvie, Phyllis	Acadia University	Psychology Department
Ibrahim, Selahadin	Institute for Work & Health	
Kelloway, E. Kevin	Saint Mary's University	Department of Management
Larocque, Brigitte	CHA Québec	Unité de recherche en santé des populations
Laschinger, Heather K.	University of Western Ontario	School of Nursing
Leiter, Michael	Acadia University	Psychology Department
Lendrum, Bonnie	McMaster University	School of Nursing
McDonough, Peggy	University of Toronto	Department of Public Health Sciences
Mergler, Donna	UQÀM	Department des sciences biologiques - CINBIOSE
Messing, Karen	UQÀM	Department des sciences biologiques - CINBIOSE
Mishara, Brian Leslie	UQÀM	CRISE
Moisan, Jocelyne	Université Laval	Groupe de Recherche en Epidemiologie
Mustard, Cam	Institute for Work & Health	
Norton, Ron	University of Winnipeg	Department of Psychology
Patten, Scott B.	University of Calgary	Department of Psychiatry
Regehr, Cheryl	University of Toronto	School of Social Work
Shamian, Judith	Health Canada	Nursing Policy Office
Shannon, Harry	McMaster University	Department of Clinical Epidemiology & Biostatistics
Smart, Reginald G.	CAMH	Addiction Research Foundation Division
Stewart, N.J.	University of Saskatchewan	College of Nursing
Vézina, Michel	Université Laval	Département de médecine sociale et préventive
Walters, Vivienne	McMaster University	Department of Sociology
Woodward, Christel	McMaster University	Community Care Research Centre

* Chercheurs ayant au moins trois publications au cours de la période 1991-2002.

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

6. Conclusion

Le champ de la santé mentale en milieu de travail (SMMT) est une entreprise scientifique à l'état naissant. Quoique l'importance économique de la SMMT soit bien reconnue, seulement environ un cinquième d'un pour cent des publications biomédicales se penchent sur cette question. Malgré cette faible production, le champ croît en termes absolus à l'échelle mondiale, allant de 535 publications indexées dans Medline en 1991 à 940 en 2002 – soit une croissance de 75 % en 12 ans.

Bien qu'en général la production soit encore peu élevée, la recherche en SMMT augmente plus rapidement au Canada qu'à l'échelle mondiale. Pendant les trois dernières années, le nombre de publications effectué au Canada a triplé : il représente maintenant 5,5 % de la production mondiale dans ce champ. Le Canada se spécialise dans ce champ, ayant une proportion de publications en SMMT qui est 20 % plus élevée que celle de Medline au cours de la période 1991-2002.

Au Canada, l'Ontario est sans contredit le chef de file. Il produit 46 % de la production canadienne et se classe deuxième en publications par personne et troisième selon l'indice de spécialisation. Bien que la Nouvelle-Écosse et le Manitoba n'occupent pas une place prépondérante en termes absolus, ils se classent correctement en matière de publications par personne et d'indice de spécialisation.

Les villes les plus actives dans le champ sont Toronto et Montréal, tandis que Vancouver, London et Hamilton ont au moins deux publications sur la SMMT par année en moyenne. Chose peu étonnante, les institutions qui occupent les premières places en importance dans ce champ – McMaster University, Université de Montréal, University of Toronto, University of British Columbia et University of Western Ontario – se situent dans ces mêmes villes.

Les trois quarts des vingt chercheurs qui publient le plus dans ce champ proviennent de ces universités. McMaster et Laval ont le plus grand nombre de chercheurs de premier rang (quatre chercheurs chacun), tandis que la York University a deux chercheurs de premier rang dans le champ.

Les statistiques présentées dans ce rapport montrent que l'activité scientifique dans le champ demeure faible. Ainsi, la loi des grands nombres ne s'applique peut-être pas encore, et l'on devrait s'attendre à observer, dans les années à venir, une certaine inconstance dans le classement des entités de premier rang – qu'il s'agisse des provinces, des villes, des institutions ou des chercheurs. Ce rapport fournit une indication de la recherche dans le champ aux premiers stades de son développement, et l'on peut s'attendre à voir des changements dans la distribution géographique des activités au fur et à mesure que le champ évoluera dans la prochaine décennie.

Annexe 1. Nombre de publications sur la SMMT par province et par ville, 1991-2002

Province	Ville	1991-1993	1994-1996	1997-1999	2000-2002	TOTAL
Ontario						177
	Toronto	11	16	19	33	79
	London	4	3	11	10	28
	Hamilton	3	5	9	9	26
	Ottawa	3	1	5	7	16
	Kingston	2	1	3	3	9
	Guelph	1	1	3		5
	Sudbury	1	1	2	1	5
	Windsor			1	2	3
	St. Catharines		2			2
	Waterloo			2		2
	Brockville	1				1
	Collingwood		1			1
Québec						80
	Montréal	11	8	18	18	55
	Québec	1	5	7	6	19
	Rimouski	1				1
	Sherbrooke	1		1	2	4
	Trois-Rivières			1		1
Colombie-Britannique						36
	Vancouver	4	4	10	11	30
	Victoria		2		1	3
	Prince George				2	2
	Salmon Arm			1		1
Alberta						34
	Edmonton	7	2	3	7	19
	Calgary	1	1	1	7	10
	Lethbridge	1	1	1		3
	Red Deer			1		1
	Fort McMurray				1	1
Nouvelle-Écosse						20
	Halifax	3	2	1	6	13
	Wolfville		1	4	1	6
	Sydney			1		1
Manitoba						19
	Winnipeg	4	8	4	3	19
Saskatchewan						10
	Saskatoon	1	1	2	2	6
	Regina		2		2	4
Nouveau-Brunswick						2
	Moncton		1			1
	Saint John				1	1
Terre-Neuve						2
	St. John's	1			1	2
Île-du-Prince-Édouard						1
	Charlottetown			1		1
TOTAL	Canada	62	69	113	137	381

Source : Compilé par Science-Metrix à partir de la base de données Medline.

Annexe 2. Chercheurs ayant publié au moins une publication sur la SMMT avec un canadien comme premier auteur, 1991-2002

Abenhaim, L	Beaton, R	Braun, K	Christenson, J M
Abrams, Karen M	Beaudet, M P	Bremner, R	Clarke, D
Acorn, S	Beaudry, J	Bricault, N	Clements, Paul T
Adlaf, E M	Beaumont, L	Brillon, P	Clifford, Tammy J
Adler, S	Bedard, D	Brisson, R J	Cockerill, Rhonda
Adrian, M	Begin, S	Brisson, C	Cohen, C
Agro, K	Beiser, M	Brisson, J	Colantonio, A
Alary, M	Beland, Francois	Brodeur, J	Cole, D C
Ali, J	Belanger, B	Brophy, J T	Collins, E
Allard, P	Belanger, S	Brotheridge, Celeste M	Collins, P I
Allen, C	Bell, C E	Brown, G T	Colotla, V A
Allerdings, M D	Bellavance, F	Brown, J	Comeau, M
Alleyne, B C	Benard, J	Brown, J B	Conlon, M
Allison, D G	Bergeron, R	Brown, K D	Connaughty, S
Almost, J	Berkowitz, J	Brown-DeGagne, A M	Connelly, I
Alvarado, Beatriz E	Best, J A	Browne, G	Cook, J V
Andermann, F	Bhaskara, S M	Bruce, Shirliana	Cook, K
Antony, M M	Bienefeld, M	Brunet, A	Copes, R
Arklie, M	Binkley, K E	Bryant, H E	Corbin, S
Armstron-Esther, C A	Birch, Stephen	Buckley, Richard E	Cormier, N
Armstrong, B	Blackford, K A	Bullock, L	Corneil, W
Armstrong-Stassen, M	Blackhouse, G	Burke, R J	Cossette, S
Arsenault, A	Blair, Nancy	Bury, Alison S	Coupland, N J
Ashforth, B E	Blake, J	Byrne, C	Couture, R T
Asmundson, G J	Blanchard, R	Cadsky, O	Coutu-Wakulczyk, G M
Aston, J	Blanchette, C	Calvert, B L	Craven, M A
Aubin, Ginette	Block, L	Camfield, C	Crockett, D J
Aubin, M	Bobocel, D R	Camfield, P	Crowe, J
Auger, C	Boivin, Diane B	Campbell, M Karen	Crustolo, A M
Averill, Jennifer B	Bonin, M F	Cann, B	Culp, D
Avison, W R	Boon, L	Cantin, B	Cunningham, C E
Avotri, J Y	Boucher, C	Cargo, M	Cunningham, D A
Baba, V V	Boudreau, R A	Carlson, D	Dab, W
Bagby, R Michael	Bourassa, D C	Carlson, P	Dagenais, G R
Bailey, P A	Bourassa, M	Caron, Staci	Daigle, M S
Bailey, P H	Bourbonnais, R	Carron, A V	Daines, P A
Bairati, I	Bourdouxhe, M A	Casey, A	D'Arcy, Carl
Baker, B	Bourgault, C	Centerwall, A R	David, M
Bakker, D	Bourgine, M	Chalifour, J	Davidson, S
Baldwin, M	Boustead, R	Chambers, L W	Davies, B
Bardon, E	Bouthillette, F	Chan-Yeung, M	Davies, Sharon
Barham, L	Boutilier, M A	Chappell, N L	Davis, J R
Baril, R H	Bowen, P	Charpentier, Nicole	Day, A L
Barling, J	Bowman, M L	Chartrand, E	Day, M
Barnes, G E	Boyer, G	Chehaitly, A	de Bosset, F
Barrette, Jacques	Boyer, R	Chen, S	de Man, A F
Basinski, A	Boyle, M	Cherry, N M	Dean, R A
Baylard, J F	Bradford, J	Chilcott, L A	Deaudelin, C
Bean, G	Brandon, R A	Choudhry, U	Del Ser, Teodoro
Beaton, D	Brands, B	Choy, T	Delmas, Philippe

DeLuca, V M	FitzGibbon, G M	Gregoire, M	Ibrahim, S A
Demers, P A	Fleetham, J A	Gregor, F	Iezzi, A
Denney, D	Flemons, W W	Gregory, D	Infante-Rivard, C
Dennis, R	Ford, J S	Grenier, J L	Irvine, J
Denton, Margaret	Fortier, I	Griffith, L	Irvine, M J
Dewa, C S	Fortin, M	Grunfeld, E	Isaacs, S
Dion, G	Foster, S	Grypma, S	Isbister, W
Dolan, S L	Foucault, C	Grzybowski, S	Iverson, G L
Donald, J	Fournier, Marc A	Guertin, S C	Iwasaki, Y
Dooley, J	Fraboni, M	Guidotti, T L	Jackson, D N
Doran, Diane	Frankel, S	Guilleminault, C	Jackson, T
Dow-Clarke, R Anne	Fraser, K L	Guruge, S	Jacobson, S J
Dowin, S	Freeman, S J	Guyatt, G	Jacono, B J
Downie, F	French, S	Haase, Mary	Jacono, J J
Drolet, D	Frizzell, C	Hachey, R	Jamal, M
Ducharme, F	Frombach, I K	Hafer, C	James, Francine O
Duchscher, J E	Frost, P	Hagey, R	Jewers, R
Dugbartey, A T	Fry, P S	Hall, B	Johnson, C
Dumais, L	Gafni, Amiram	Hall, W	Johnson, P J
Dumais, W	Gagnon, M	Haney, Colleen J	Johnson, R L
Dunlop, R	Galperin, B L	Hanson, E J	Johnston, J
Dunn, K W	Garci, Linda J	Hanson, R K	Jones, B
Dupuis, M	Garside, B	Harkness, Kate L	Jones, E
Duquette, A	Gaskowski, P	Harrick, L	Jones, M W
Durand, Marie-Jose	Gauthier, R	Harris, A	Jones, N
Dussault, M	Geddes, J	Harrison, Margaret J	Joyce, Anthony S
Dyck, Dianne	Gerber, G J	Harrisson, Madelaine	Jreige, Steve
Dyck, Isabel	Gerlach, Jacquelyn	Harvie, P	Julien, D
Eaves, D	Lochhaas	Harwood, G	Juniper, E F
Edwards, R G	Gerrish, R	Havens, D S	Kaasalainen, Sharon
Egan, S	Getty, L	Havlovic, S J	Kaminski, M
Ehrensaft, E	Gibson, B	Hawkins, R H	Kane, D
Ehrmann Feldman, D	Gien, L T	Hellyer, D	Kaspar, V
Erickson, D	Giguere, J	Hemsworth, D	Kates, N
Ernst, P	Giles-Fysh, N	Hendy, K C	Katic, M
Escalona, E	Gillrie, C	Hepburn, C G	Katz, J
Esdaile, J M	Gingras, S	Herbert, Carol P	Kaufert, P A
Eskes, G A	Giroux, G	Herman, E	Kaufmann, C
Evans, W K	Gladue, R	Hershler, R	Keddy, B
Everett, A M	Glancy, G	Hertzman, C	Keenan, S P
Eyles, J	Gliksman, L	Hetu, R	Keith, M M
Farant, J P	Godwin, M	Hibberd, J M	Kelloway, E K
Farewell, V T	Goeree, R	Higginbottom, S F	Kelly, S
Fargas-Babjak, A	Goering, P	Hilditch, J R	Kerouac, S
Farrar, S	Gold, N	Hill, J	Kerr, K L
Feather, J	Goldberg, G	Hodgetts, G	Kerr, M
Feeny, D	Gordon, K	Hodgins, D C	King, A
Feinstein, Anthony	Gorodzinsky, Fabian	Holness, D L	King, W D
Ferguson, K A	Gottlieb, B H	Hong, Quan Nha	Kinzel, A
Ferguson-Pare, M	Grafstein, E	Hope, L	Kishchuk, N
Fernandes, C M	Graham, K	Hou, F	Kivisto, J
Fillion, Joel S	Granger, D	House, R A	Klinger, L
Finegan, J	Green, L W	Howell, Andrew J	Knoefel, F
Finestone, H M	Green, P	Hughes, D	Knoop, R
Fischer, B	Greenglass, E R	Hylton, J H	Knott, Theresa
Fitch, M	Gregg, Robin	Iacono, W G	Koch, W J

Kojlak, J	Lillywhite, A	McKee, M D	Nikolaou, L
Konarski, R	Lin, E	McKelvie, R	Nilsson, T
Kositsky, A J	Lippel, K	McKessock, D	Nisker, J A
Kotteda, V	Lituchy, T R	McLeod, K	Noble, E G
Krahn, Harvey	Livingstone, H A	McLeod, R B	Noh, S
Kraus, R P	Lloyd, S	McMahon, L	Norman, R M
Kraut, A	Locker, D	McMillan, C	Norris, J
Kruse, K	Logan, A G	McNally, R J	Northcott, H C
Kuch, K	Loisel, Patrick	McRae, M P	Norton, G R
Kumar, S	Loiselle, Carmen G	Mead, Shery	Norton, P G
Kunz, J L	Loiselle, J	Medved, W	Norton, P J
Kushner, Kaysi Eastlick	Loney, P	Mercier, C	Novak, M
Labreche, F P	Loo, R	Mergler, D	Nutt, D J
Lachance, L	Lord, C	Messing, K	Oberle, K
Laflamme, N	Love, E J	Metz, L M	O'Brien, B J
Laforce, R Jr	Luescher, U A	Metzler, T J	O'Brien, Patti
Lafreniere, K	Lusk, C	Meyer, F	O'Brien-Pallas, Linda
Laing, M K	MacDonald, G	Middleton, J I	Offord, D
Lalonde, C	MacDonald, N E	Mignone, J	Ogborne, A C
Laroche, Chantal	Macdonald, S	Milgram, P	Ogilvie, R
Larocque, B	Macerollo, J	Miller, L	Ogloff, J R
Larocque, D	MacEwen, K E	Milliken, H	Ogrodniczuk, John S
Larribe, F	Mackenzie, B	Milne, R	O'Hara, P L
Larsen, D K	Mackinnon, J R	Milot, A	Ohayon, M M
Laschinger, H K	MacLaren, V V	Minnes, P	O'Kelly, B
Latimer, E A	Malla, A K	Mishara, B L	O'Kelly, J
Latour, S	Mann, R E	Mital, A	Oldridge, N
Laundry, B R	Mannell, R C	Mitchell, G J	O'Loane, M
Laurent, C	Marcoux, S	Mohr, E	Olsen, L
Lavanchy, M	Marion, S A	Moisan, J	Ostry, A S
Lavery, J	Markle-Reid, Maureen	Mondor, M	Ouellet, L
Leach, A J	Marmar, C R	Monroe, Scott M	Owen, John
Leach, P	Marriott, A	Montesanto, B	Ozanne, W G
LeBlanc, Manon Mireille	Martin, G L	Moore, C F	Pace, A
Leclaire, R	Maslach, C	Moore, L	Packer, D
Lee, R	Mason, R A	Morehouse, R	Page, Eileen P
Lee, R T	Masse, B	Morgan, Debra G	Palepu, Anita
Lee, Raymond T	Massicotte, P R	Morrison, H I	Palla, Linda L O'Brien
Lees, M C	Maurier, W L	Mortenson, Patricia	Passey, G
Lees, R E	May, K A	Moskowitz, D S	Paterson, D H
Legault, E	Mayr, J	Moszczynski, Alice B	Paterson, Michael
Leigh, G	Mayville, K	Mueser, Kim T	Patrick, L
Leiter, M P	McAfee, J G	Mulder, J	Patten, S B
Lemay, F	McAiney, C A	Murnaghan, M Lucas	Patton, D
Lemieux, A P	McCain, G A	Murphy, S	Paul, J
Lendrum, B	McCall, M	Murray, M	Peat, J K
Lenton, R	McCallum, M	Murray, Michael	Perrault, G
Lepage, D	McColl, Mary Ann	Murray, R P	Perusse, M
LeSage, P	McCormick, J	Mustard, C	Pesut, B
Levesque, L	McDonald, C	Muzin, F	Peternej-Taylor, C A
Levy, B A	McDonald, J C	Myles, W S	Peters, C
Levy, M	McDonough, Peggy	Myrick, Florence	Pettigrew, F P
Lewis, J	McDowell, I	Nanson, J	Philibert, L
Leznoff, A	McIndoe, K I	Nelson, T M	Phipps, L
Lian, Jason	McIntosh, J	Newbold, B	Pickett, W
Liao, J	McIntyre, J W	Nicholson, I R	Pike, K

Piper, W E	Sale, Joanna E M	Stoddart, Greg	Vinje, G
Plotkin, D	Salmi, L R	Stratford, P	Vyskocil, A
Polatajko, H J	Sandhu, B K	Streiner, D	Wakeling, H
Polimeni-Walker, I	Sanford, M	Stringer, B	Wall, R
Pongruengphant, R	Sassine, M P	Strohschein, Lisa	Wald, R
Potokar, J P	Saulnier, P	Stuart, P	Walsh, G
Pranger, T	Saurel-Cubizolles, M J	Stutzer, C	Walsh, G W
Priest, R G	Savard, J	Suedfeld, P	Walters, V
Proulx, R	Sawka, E	Suissa, S	Wang, J
Provencher, Helene L	Schechter, J	Sullivan, T	Waridel, S
Queinnec, Y	Schell, B H	Swenson, J R	Waters, B G
Raboud, J M	Schemitsch, E H	Sylvestre, M	Watson, David C
Rae, S	Schlosar, H	Szalai, J P	Watson, J
Ratner, P A	Schmidt, G	Tanguay, S M	Watterson, A
Rebeiro, K L	Scholten, D	Tardif, R	Way, M
Rector, N A	Schopler, E	Tate, R	Weber, W
Regehr, C	Scott, F E	Taylor, A W	Weiss, D S
Regehr, G	Seguin, R	Taylor, S	Wells, S
Rehm, J	Seifert, A M	Teasell, R W	Whelan, T J
Rehm, J	Semchuk, Karen M	Teschke, K	Wiebe, J
Reid, Doreen	Semenic, Sonia E	Tett, R P	Wiele, K
Reilly, S M	Sewitch, M J	Thommasen, H V	Wild, T C
Reutter, L I	Sexton, L	Thomson, Donna	Wilk, P
Rexroth, D	Shain, M	Thurston, N E	Wilkins, K
Rhodes, A	Shamian, J	Tien, G	Willan, A R
Richard, L	Shannon, H S	Tipliski, V M	Williams, K
Richardsen, A M	Shapiro, C M	Tobe, S W	Williams, R
Richardson, J S	Shaw, Brenda Laurie	Torrance, G	Williams-Keeler, L
Rivard, G E	Sheehy, O	Towers, A M	Willmer, J
Roach, Sally M	Shercliffe, R J	Townsend, E A	Wilson, K G
Roberts, J	Shields, M	Trojan, Lorraine	Wishart, L
Robichaud, L	Shrier, Ian	Trott, M	Wong, C
Robinson, Gail Erlick	Shulman, K I	Truchon, G	Woodcox, V
Robinson, S	Sibbald, W J	Trudel, M	Wood-Dauphinee, S
Robson, L	Sidani, Souraya	Tsai, W	Woodward, C A
Rodgers, C D	Sinclair, D E	Tully, S	Woolfenden, S R
Roesch, R	Singer, J	Turner, R J	Wowk, A
Rogers, H L	Single, E	Turritin, J	Wu, Z
Rogers, J M	Skelton-Green, J	Tyson, P D	Xie, X
Rogers, K A	Smart, R G	Tziner, A	Yonge, Olive
Roithmayr, Tony	Smith, B	Underwood, J	Yoo, D
Rondeau, K V	Smith, C A	Vachon, M L	Young, A
Rook, M	Smith, D	Van Ameringen, M R	Zacharatos, A
Rosenbloom, D	Smylie, J A	van der Wal, R	Zaza, C
Rosie, John S	Spaulding, S J	van Netten, C	Zeitlin, S B
Ross, H E	Speechley, Kathy N	Vedantham, K	Zeytinoglu, Isik Urla
Rossignol, M	Speechley, M	Venter, A	Zhang, J
Roth, D	Staley, D	Vermeulen, M	Zimmerman, G
Rousseau, A	Steel, G D	Vernich, L	Zirul, S
Royer, N	Stephenson, R	Vezina, L	Zitzelsberger, L
Runions, J	Stewart, D E	Vezina, M	Zunzunegui, Maria-
Russell, Grant M	Stewart, J	Vigil, Gloria J	Victoria
Rzasa, T	Stewart, N J	Villeneuve, M	Zuroff, David C
Salama, P	Stieb, D	Vinet, A	Zuzanek, J

Annexe 3. Publications sur la SMMT avec un canadien comme premier auteur, 1991-2002

- 1: Abrams KM, Robinson GE. Occupational effects of stalking. *Can J Psychiatry*. 2002 Jun; 47(5): 468-72.
- 2: Acorn S. Head-injured survivors: caregivers and support groups. *J Adv Nurs*. 1993 Jan; 18(1): 39-45.
- 3: Adlaf EM, Smart RG, Walsh GW. Substance use and work disabilities among a general population. *Am J Drug Alcohol Abuse*. 1992; 18(4): 371-87.
- 4: Ali J, Avison WR. Employment transitions and psychological distress: the contrasting experiences of single and married mothers. *J Health Soc Behav*. 1997 Dec; 38(4): 345-62.
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- 6: Allison DG. Assessing stress among public school principals in British Columbia. *Psychol Rep*. 1997 Jun; 80(3 Pt 2): 1103-14.
- 7: Almost J, Laschinger HK. Workplace empowerment, collaborative work relationships, and job strain in nurse practitioners. *J Am Acad Nurse Pract*. 2002 Sep; 14(9): 408-20.
- 8: Alvarado BE, Zunzunegui MV, Del Ser T, Beland F. Cognitive decline is related to education and occupation in a Spanish elderly cohort. *Aging Clin Exp Res*. 2002 Apr; 14(2): 132-42.
- 9: Armstrong-Esther CA, Brown KD, McAfee JG. Elderly patients: still clean and sitting quietly. *J Adv Nurs*. 1994 Feb; 19(2): 264-71.
- 10: Armstrong-Stassen M. Reactions of older employees to organizational downsizing: the role of gender, job level, and time. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci*. 2001 Jul; 56(4): P234-43.
- 11: Asmundson GJ, Bonin MF, Frombach IK, Norton GR. Evidence of a disposition toward fearfulness and vulnerability to posttraumatic stress in dysfunctional pain patients. *Behav Res Ther*. 2000 Aug; 38(8): 801-12.
- 12: Asmundson GJ, Norton GR, Allardings MD, Norton PJ, Larsen DK. Posttraumatic stress disorder and work-related injury. *J Anxiety Disord*. 1998 Jan-Feb; 12(1): 57-69.
- 13: Asmundson GJ, Jacobson SJ, Allardings MD, Norton GR. Social phobia in disabled workers with chronic musculoskeletal pain. *Behav Res Ther*. 1996 Nov-Dec; 34(11-12): 939-43.
- 14: Aston J, Lavery J. The health of women in paid employment: effects of quality of work role, social support and cynicism on psychological and physical well-being. *Women Health*. 1993; 20(3): 1-25.
- 15: Aubin G, Hachey R, Mercier C. [The significance of daily activities in persons with severe mental disorders] *Can J Occup Ther*. 2002 Oct; 69(4): 218-28. French.
- 16: Aubin M, Vezina L, Allard P, Bergeron R, Lemieux AP. [Palliative care: profile of medical practice in the Quebec city region] *Can Fam Physician*. 2001 Oct; 47: 1999-2005. French.
- 17: Auger C, Latour S, Trudel M, Fortin M. [Post-traumatic stress disorder. After the flood in Saguenay] *Can Fam Physician*. 2000 Dec; 46(12): 2420-7. French.
- 18: Avotri JY, Walters V. "You just look at our work and see if you have any freedom on earth": Ghanaian women's accounts of their work and their health. *Soc Sci Med*. 1999 May; 48(9): 1123-33.

- 19: A benhaim L, Dab W, Salmi LR. Study of civilian victims of terrorist attacks (France 1982-1987). *J Clin Epidemiol.* 1992 Feb; 45(2): 103-9.
- 20: Baba VV, Galperin BL, Lituchy TR. Occupational mental health: a study of work-related depression among nurses in the Caribbean. *Int J Nurs Stud.* 1999 Apr; 36(2): 163-9.
- 21: Baker B, O'Kelly B, Szalai JP, Katic M, McKessock D, Ogilvie R, Basinski A, Tobe SW. Determinants of left ventricular mass in early hypertension. *Am J Hypertens.* 1998 Oct; 11(10): 1248-51.
- 22: Barling J, Zacharatos A, Hepburn CG. Parents' job insecurity affects children's academic performance through cognitive difficulties. *J Appl Psychol.* 1999 Jun; 84(3): 437-44.
- 23: Barling J, MacEwen KE, Kelloway EK, Higginbottom SF. Predictors and outcomes of elder-care-based interrole conflict. *Psychol Aging.* 1994 Sep; 9(3): 391-7.
- 24: Bedard D, Duquette A. [Professional exhaustion, a concept to be clarified] *Infirm Que.* 1998 Sep-Oct; 6(1): 18-23. Review. French. No abstract available.
- 25: Begin S, Gregoire M. [Causal relations of occupational psychiatric disability] *Can J Psychiatry.* 1991 Sep; 36(7): 485-91. Review. French.
- 26: Beiser M, Hou F. Language acquisition, unemployment and depressive disorder among Southeast Asian refugees: a 10-year study. *Soc Sci Med.* 2001 Nov; 53(10): 1321-34.
- 27: Beiser M, Bean G, Erickson D, Zhang J, Iacono WG, Rector NA. Biological and psychosocial predictors of job performance following a first episode of psychosis. *Am J Psychiatry.* 1994 Jun; 151(6): 857-63.
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- 29: Beiser M, Johnson PJ, Turner RJ. Unemployment, underemployment and depressive affect among Southeast Asian refugees. *Psychol Med.* 1993 Aug; 23(3): 731-43.
- 30: Beland F, Birch S, Stoddart G. Unemployment and health: contextual-level influences on the production of health in populations. *Soc Sci Med.* 2002 Dec; 55(11): 2033-52.
- 31: Best JA, Walsh G, Muzin F, Berkowitz J. Healthy hospital: toward a better tomorrow. A demonstration project to promote culture change through participatory decision making. *Healthc Manage Forum.* 1997 Fall; 10(3): 24-9, 32-3.
- 32: Bhaskara SM. Setting benchmarks and determining psychiatric workloads in community mental health programs. *Psychiatr Serv.* 1999 May; 50(5): 695-7.
- 33: Blackford KA, Bailey PH, Coutu-Wakulczyk GM. Tobacco use in northeastern Ontario teenagers: prevalence of use and associated factors. *Can J Public Health.* 1994 Mar-Apr; 85(2): 89-92.
- 34: Blanchard R, Collins PI. Men with sexual interest in transvestites, transsexuals, and she-males. *J Nerv Ment Dis.* 1993 Sep; 181(9): 570-5.
- 35: Block L. The employment connection: the application of an individual supported employment program for persons with chronic mental health problems. *Can J Commun Ment Health.* 1992 Fall; 11(2): 79-89.
- 36: Boivin DB, James FO. Circadian adaptation to night-shift work by judicious light and darkness exposure. *J Biol Rhythms.* 2002 Dec; 17(6): 556-67.
- 37: Boon L. Caring practices and the financial bottom line. *Can Nurse.* 1998 Mar; 94(3): 27-32.
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- 39: Bourassa DC, Levy BA, Dowin S, Casey A. Transfer effects across contextual and linguistic boundaries: evidence from poor readers. *J Exp Child Psychol.* 1998 Oct; 71(1): 45-61.
- 40: Bourassa M, Baylard JF. Stress situations in dental practice. *J Can Dent Assoc.* 1994 Jan; 60(1): 65-7, 70-1.
- 41: Bourbonnais R, Mondor M. Job strain and sickness absence among nurses in the province of Quebec. *Am J Ind Med.* 2001 Feb; 39(2): 194-202.
- 42: Bourbonnais R, Comeau M, Vezina M. Job strain and evolution of mental health among nurses. *J Occup Health Psychol.* 1999 Apr; 4(2): 95-107.
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